

Parametric optimization of stent design based on FE analysis

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Abstract— Endovascular prosthesis - stents are used as a solution for treating many health disorders and diseases. Their major application is found in treating cardio-vascular diseases. One of the problems in stent implantation is a process called in stent restenosis (ISR). In the pre-stent era, the occurrence of restenosis ranged between 32-55% of all angioplasties, and in bare-metal stent (BMS) era this range dropped to 17-41%. Many factors have influence on this phenomenon. Some studies show that in stent restenosis, strut shape and thickness have significant impact, especially if the stent is implanted in the small arteries. For better stent geometry modeling, in this paper authors suggested novel approach – para-metric optimization on the existing stent design.

I. INTRODUCTION

The complications associated with endovascular stents treatment have become manifest and include restenosis [1], stent migration, proximal neck dilation, and endoleak [2]. These complications can be overcome with the good selection and adjustment physical and mechanical properties of the endovascular stents. Several studies shown that the shape and thickness of the stent strut have a significant effect on these complications, especially on restenosis. [6]. Our purpose in this study was to examine the new atomically approach for geometry optimization. Aim of optimization is to stent preserve same radial force, stress and strain with significant strut thickness reduction. Our hypotheses were that it is possible with new approach of optimizing from old stent model (model from the market place) to get a newest design with same mechanical characteristic but with significant smaller strut thickness and potentially with less complications.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Parametric optimisation

In a complex process of product development and production environments, designers and engineers have to use a wide range of software tools to design and simulate their products. In the complex optimization process, several thousand simulations need to be performed over some work. This process requires a lot of manual work and time. The parametric analysis itself is performed in a closed loop that needs to be done many times.

Figure 1. Unique segment of the stent model with geometric parameters that define the entire model

The geometry of the initial model was created based on the geometry parameters from real Palmaz-Schatz stent model on the market. (Fig. 1)

The technique that was used for optimization is Pointer. This technique is used for automatic optimization and it contains a set of several standard optimization algorithms.

- Genetic algorithm [4].
- Nelder and Mead downhill simplex [5].
- NLPQL -Non-Linear Programming by Quadratic Lagrangian.[6]
- Linear Solver.

III. RESULTS

Manual analysis of such a large number of models would require time. By introducing the optimization algorithms, the problem is solved in 117 steps. Using novel optimization approach system generate a several possibility of new stent designs based on some existing design. On this easy way old design is very much improved. New design has the same distribution of strain but significantly less strut cross section. This is huge advantage because this stent will produce less in-stent restenosis in patient and decresies number of complications. The aim of this paper is to present new methods for fast and easy optimization process in designing stents. These methods can greatly facilitate the process of stent de-sign in the future and prevent possible “expensive” mistakes that are detected at a later stage of prototype testing.

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* Research supported by the grants: EC This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 689068 and No 777119, and III41007 and ON174028 Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of Serbia.

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